

Mind Theory: What on Earth are we?

A quick appraisal: a species with remarkable technical prowess suffering from lack of self-control; and, yes, we are an animal species. I will describe our biological niche – which is perhaps not quite how you might have thought of it. In fact, understanding our niche is the key to understanding ourselves.

First, the big picture: now that we have a good idea of the scale and nature of the Universe, few can reasonably doubt the existence of countless locations that could potentially support life and that, in view of the time spans involved, they will be occupied by living organisms. There must be life everywhere in the Universe, albeit very thinly scattered and isolated. This is the context of life on Earth.

The essential conditions for life everywhere satisfy the requirements of organic chemical reactions, and, given enough time, more complex products of those reactions appear that are able to process information in a way that ensures that they survive long enough to grow by making copies of themselves. Given more time, those products will evolve into what are recognisably living, reproducing organisms. These organisms too can be thought of as 'processing information' about their environments; information is an integral part of their biochemistry and, in the more sophisticated products of evolution, distinct 'brains' have precisely the function of processing information. Doing it successfully explains why a host of species existed in the past and others manage to exist now; but obviously it doesn't explain everything. In a changing world, continuing existence is a matter of luck too. Happily, many might say, the story of life is not only a question of existence: reproduction provides the *élan vital* that causes the river of life-forms to flow into a variety of environments where they are able to thrive. At a more local level, these accommodating environments are called niches. We are part of the stream of life and we can think of ourselves as occupying a particular niche.

The next point might surprise: we have fallen into a *universal* niche. In addition to the physical environments in which life first evolves, a behavioural niche exists, everywhere – just patiently waiting to be filled, one might say. On this planet, we filled it. It is a niche opened up by being able to handle information, not just the information

integrated with our bodies and our biochemistry, but an abstract form of information. We occupy the niche opened up on this planet by the ability to handle abstract information - in the form of language - 'intelligently'. It is inevitable that other life forms (in galaxies far, far away) tumble into this niche, thrive and chatter to each other about it. It's just a question of time.

So what happened here, at home? We are the descendants of social animals that developed a language for communication. Their brains adapted to the considerable challenge of using language to construct a social identity, unique for each individual, and the brain activity that results from this identity is 'the mind'. The use of language involves abstraction and it is the ability of our minds to 'handle' abstract symbols – just as we use our hands to put things together and take them apart – that has opened up the niche that we occupy. I should point out straight away that the concept of 'abstract' is a trap for the unwary; it does *not* mean that information has adopted any kind of spiritual form, so that when we communicate using abstract symbols, our minds have access to a virtual, parallel universe. Nothing 'abstract', and that includes 'information', ever escapes from a material world in flux. More than that, and most importantly, we do not process information in the manner of a computer: it is crucial to remember that living organisms always tag information with values, of the kind “will I survive; will I reproduce?”. In our particular case, the signs and symbols of language are indivisible from their values - which are inevitably social values. We have vital concerns in addition to individual survival because each of us needs to establish a stable identity and 'survive' in society.

A key aspect of our use of information is that we found a way of passing it reliably back and forth between autonomous individuals who are free to decide what to do with it. There have been centuries of debate over just how 'free' we are; so let's just say for the purpose of this discussion that we are free *enough*; and clearly we are not identical. Therein lies our need to create language rules that we agree on, and codes of meaning and value that, once again, we agree on (more or less; there's the rub). The source of our ability not only to survive and dominate but also to adapt and change mentally – and therefore culturally - is the step from one brain to many communicating minds. In a sense, what happens between many minds is a scaled-up version of what happens in one brain: the neurones of the brain communicate meaningfully using codes with a long evolutionary history when they pass information between each other; but neurones are slaves, not autonomous, and that accounts for the difference between what one brain can achieve compared to many and various minds.

If these remarks seem reasonable, you will see that we are one example of a kind of animal that will inevitably appear at some time, somewhere in the Universe. (Birds, bats and insects might say the same, if it were possible, about their mastery of flight; but the existence of a medium suitable for flight everywhere there is life is less certain than the absolute certainty of the universal existence of our information-handling niche.) Being labelled as 'inevitable' implies that it is not helpful to see ourselves as simply an

accidental outcome of blind evolution. Evolution certainly is blind and involves copious doses of accident, but sooner or later, life forms will stumble on fruitful niches, and we stumbled into this one. We are not unique in the way that we are tempted to think of ourselves as unique, because there must be (will be, must have been, alas) a host of species scattered throughout the Universe that we could identify with because we could, in principle, communicate with them. They will be social creatures with language and minds, because that's the successful niche – as we have demonstrated it – that they occupy. They must also have feelings and emotions that we would recognise as such because emotions are not only the reflexes that keep animals with brains physically intact, they are also an essential part of a social identity.

So, not surprisingly, it is our mind that is at the centre of understanding who we are. To be clearer about ourselves it is necessary to get a better understanding of the way the mind works.

The key to understanding the mind is thinkish. Thinkish is a convenient name for what can be pictured as a collection of neurones in the brain that represent language fragments linked together by routines by which these fragments are used when 'thinking'. Thoughts and speech are constructed from thinkish, which therefore represents the neuronal basis of our mind.

To illustrate what I am getting at, I carried out a thought experiment.

(The diagram is just a diagram, not neuroanatomy.)

This is the experiment: a piece of donor thinkish is transplanted into the existing thinkish of the brain of a volunteer...

This new thinkish is now available to the thought-constructing system of the recipient brain, which, in theory, can use it to create thoughts implicating the thinkish of the transplant. Thinkish is normally converted into thoughts that express the social identity of its owner, so the question is: how will the brain deal with the alien thinkish of the transplant?

The first try, a fault of experimental design that turned out to be revealing, used a Japanese donor and an English recipient (me). I found that I was not able to construct coherent thoughts from the donor thinkish because my brain does not understand Japanese. I found myself uttering from time to time 'Japanese' sounds that a Japanese listener might have recognised, but they were meaningless to my ears. They were surely not coherent Japanese speech either, because thinkish fragments need to be stitched together using the rules of language to create a language of communication between individuals; and my brain has not acquired the rules of Japanese.

Next, I found a suitable English-speaking donor. I imagine that this new thinkish transplant was successfully incorporated into my existing thinkish. How did this happen? It surely wasn't accepted as part of my identity by reasoning, because I cannot get into my thinkish by introspection, much as I would like to. What seems likely is that it was dreamed in. That is to say that the continual process of irrigation that keeps my existing thinkish neurones on their toes (whatever form it may take) also irrigated the transplant, and I may get some inkling of this process if I happen to dream (that is: pay dozy attention to the process of thinkish irrigation) at the right moment. Maybe the dream material will seem alien, maybe it won't; difficult to say, because dreams are pretty weird anyway. In other words, it is always going to be difficult to know whether anything took place at all.

Was it necessary to put myself, not to mention the donors, at risk in this kind of experiment? Why did I go to all this trouble? Didn't 'my' thinkish develop from transplants of donor thinkish, placed there in my infancy by caring adults? We are all living thought experiments! This is the idea...

I have pictured thinkish fragments as modular: let's say wooden blocks with some words on. A parent puts a block into junior's thinkish 'playpen', initially empty. More wooden blocks are tossed in, mostly from parents, but not only; it depends on the family environment. The infant's brain plays with its wooden blocks and passively copies the language fragments represented by the blocks – the nascent thinkish. Notice the expression 'passively copies' – copying is, and continues to be, an essential part of the process, and only later, when a mind has developed, can there be any editorial control. In the early stages the brain copies as best it can because, by so doing, the brain is on track to make sense of the world and its owner's identity in it. The language fragment-blocks represent 'information' about the world, but as I stressed in the introductory comments, not only. In fact, particularly at the early stage, the information transmitted might be slight but its value high. For example, the language bite might be: “Don't do that!” Nevertheless, continuing to play with blocks...

... you can easily imagine that the children of no two families, nor two infants in the same family, will develop the same thinkish; even though the blocks carry a common language, the relationship of the blocks will vary. This means that a fragment of language-information in one context might have nothing like the value of that same information in another. (And I have no idea which is the 'better' of these two illustrated

arrangements for our biology, our culture, the family, or the happiness of the child. But since we are looking for fixed points in a fluid situation, I guarantee that the happiness of the child is paramount. But you knew that already.)

The blocks model has its charm but it is not possible to develop a pile of blocks into an illustration of thinkish. Such an illustration is a tough ask in any case. (I have spent a long time thinking about it.) But maybe it is irrelevant to decide what the details of the structure may be in the present context, because it is essentially a problem of information-handling that the brain has had to solve, in a 'brainy' kind of way. More important here is to point out the most general feature of thinkish: that it must represent both information *and the value of that information*. But I cannot catch the essence of 'value' in an illustration such as the piles of blocks. There I intended to represent disorder/order, but if these terms give the impression of being absolute (like 'good' and 'evil'), it is an illusion. A value is a contract of meaning that guides our *behaviour*. It is therefore relative to the culture that created it and nuanced by the context in which it is expressed. So could a concept of the simplicity of the illustration have any real importance for subsequent development of the complexity of our minds, and therefore of our culture? It seems almost bizarre to reply that the answer is: yes! I need to explain. Let's say the family that contributed blocks to the blue pile felt that orderliness was boring and stifled spontaneity, while the family that chipped in the pink blocks were ill at ease with what they regarded as uncontrolled shows of emotion and the potential chaos that results. Let's now imagine that each family successfully established a clan that included some talented gardeners. What kind of garden would the gardeners of each clan create? Maybe you know already where I am going with this: the 'English Garden' and 'Versailles'. My blue clan members are happy to skip down the twisting paths leading to surprise after surprise in the English Garden, and although full of respectful admiration in the gardens of Versailles, they are not quite at home. My pink clan members are happy to enjoy what they feel are the slightly childish pleasures of the English Garden but much more at home in Versailles, where unruly Nature has been put in its place by rational minds. You can see how apparently slight differences in early-adopted values - different attitudes to 'accepting' and 'imposing', maybe – can lead to considerable divergences in the adult world. If the two clans should run into each other on the street, away from the calming influence of their gardens, 'adult' differences, to be taken oh so seriously – arising all the same from patterns of early-acquired language - might result in a quite different emotional climate. In one context, differences are reconcilable, but another may lead to... a war over which end to open a boiled egg.

In very general terms, this is how thinkish works: the process of joining fragments of language together into communicable thoughts represents information about the world; and the structures that they are drawn from represent the value of that information. Thinkish grows and develops by acquiring language information that is stored in relationships with pre-existing thinkish elements; and the relationships represent values. When these relationships are incorporated into the language of thoughts or projected out of the brain as speech, they take the form of symbols: a symbol is an economical,

compressed history of what was important in the development of the mind; it 'symbolises' values. Another way of thinking about these values would be to identify them with the feelings and emotions that we express when we use language. So the mind is doing two things: it is communicating information (what is said means something in a practical sense) and it is communicating the value of that information to the speaker. The listener will understand what is said if meanings have been agreed – they speak the same language – and will empathise with the speaker to the degree that they share values – the value of the symbols.

Hopefully it is clear from what I have said about thinkish, mind and language that values are integrated into our language and are *adopted* in one way or another. I cannot resist referring to Lamarck's fourth 'law' in biology: “*Tout ce qui a été acquis, tracé ou changé, dans l'organisation des individus, pendant le cours de leur vie, est conservé par la génération, et transmis aux nouveaux individus qui proviennent de ceux qui ont éprouvé ces changements.*” In the case of thinkish, not entirely - not 'tout' – but the principle is sound. It is one of the potential ways in which information will flow in biological systems, and we stumbled across it. If the body belongs to Darwin, the mind belongs to Lamarck.

An unavoidable consequence of the way we acquire language – in other words, our mind - is that fundamental values are acquired at a stage of the development of the mind when a critical 'editor' is not around to rationalise whether these values are best suited to the circumstances of the individual – if such an objective editor ever develops; there is nothing natural about that either. One early-acquired value might be beneficial to future development of the social life of the individual but another might be prejudicial. Everybody is aware of this state of affairs from their own experiences, (or at least they can see the problem others have), but what seems to get lost in the fog is what I said above: our identities are acquired during our lives. Take the issue of gender: how many feel that their physical gender and the state of mind that goes with it, is 'natural'? Surely the vast majority. If few nowadays would sympathise with the act of giving Alan Turing steroid hormones to 'cure' him of his homosexuality (not that long ago!), it is probably more the result of a widespread sense of tolerance than an understanding that the sexual identity, like the rest of the mind-identity, grows and develops effectively from scratch in every youngster – and can end up this way or that. Since the sexual identity is formed before the editor-mind is around, I would suggest that the brain does its best to construct a gender identity in the early days by best-guessing, guided by the overwhelming need to keep its owner happy. That Alan's young brain did its best to keep him happy but only succeeded in causing him misery in later life was not the fault of his brain but of an intolerant and prejudiced English society.

I raised the issue of gender for a reason; I have an agenda. Having two sexes that valiantly devote time and effort to jumbling up our genes is an essential part of our animal biology; and ET probably has to slog away at it too. It is a mechanism for keeping us around and physically capable of adapting to change; but we are social

animals with minds and you can see from what I said above that the sexual identity in *the mind* – or rooted in thinkish, if you like - is a cultural issue. I don't need to spell out that our sexual identities are a crucial part of who we think we are; how we act out the part has enormous personal consequences. But gender identity, seemingly as simple as the question of which garden you prefer, also has cascading consequences at the social level. How many examples are there of individuals trapped in a mental construction of their gender that have had, and continue to have, enormous influence, usually nefarious, on the world stage? Our adult minds end up being complicated, and gender is not the only issue (status is even more fundamental); but you can see where I am coming from. As much as the construction of the gender identity becomes a rigid caricature, the enactment will probably be troublesome in some way. A rigid sexual identity will be difficult to manage without raising conflict, and conflict quickly draws in issues of power, exercise of personal authority, and injustice; this much surely applies to both sexes, albeit with divergent consequences on different scales in a lop-sided world built largely with 'male' values. So there you are: one source of many of our problems, entirely created by us.

I mentioned the fundamental value of status: it is an essential feature of the universal niche. Every individual is unique and autonomous, and has a different position in their society and as a result each has a different status. Status is a broad concept, but as you can imagine from what I have said so far, the aspect of status that I am talking about is the mental picture that someone has of their place in the scheme of things. It is a thinkish construction built by the best-guessing brain from the information it gets by feedback from the society the individual is living in, a subjective assessment, tightly connected to the emotions. It is the key ingredient of the sense of well-being, and as with all fundamental mental constructions, it starts early.

However, it doesn't take long for the mind, inveterate chess-player long before chess was invented, and in cahoots with the brain, to construct a persona. The persona is the carapace of the adult mind that protects the status from hard knocks from society. As we all know, ways round the carapace remain... When something changes or goes wrong socially, the mind will do its best to adapt appropriately and re-establish an equilibrium, a point when the issue of status seems to disappear. Since an individual must construct and maintain an identity in what is a real and changing world, not surprisingly, given the overriding need for well-being, status is a pre-occupation. How much more is that the case in a culture like ours that has allowed and indeed encourages gross inequalities of status?

One of the gambits for constructing a persona can be summarised as 'strength in numbers'. The trick is to join a group with which you can identify and in which your status is more or less protected. The prototype group is the family and its tangle of emotions, so groupings in society at large will in some measure reflect the support that the family gives. This emotional *need* to form a group results in the *ability* to group up. The consequences have been crucial for our mastery of our environment (and maybe for

its destruction), because what we have achieved we have achieved collectively, by pooling our know-how, and institutions of one kind or another have become the dominant structures of society. Although the purpose of organisations and institutions is usually rational, the glue is emotional, rooted in the values acquired by individuals; maybe that is why institutions multiply our faults as well as our virtues.

However, it has not been my intention in this essay to unpick our local sociological or psychological peculiarities. Instead, I hoped to point out the importance of what I am beginning to appreciate: the *well-springs* of minds have a dominant effect on the structures and complexities of the worlds they create. The complexities we quickly get lost in are the result of the interaction of core values of the identity of individuals, irrepressibly expressed. (Dictators, on any planet, take note.) 'Minds' are the activity of brains that must establish successful social identities for their owners - the essence of 'human', et. al. They do it by handling information; and core values result from an early emotional investment in the options that govern the use of information. These options are probably no more sophisticated than: order or disorder, rigid or flexible, constant or changing... This then is the essence of our universal niche, where mind-management needs to start.

Standing back and looking at the performance of our species as a whole, it is reasonable to ask: are our pals in the Andromeda galaxy doing as well? They will have had to face the same threat: failing to understand the consequences of what they are, in time to save themselves. One major problem for a successful species will always be overpopulation, a result of good old-fashioned biology; but what we make of ourselves and our planets is going to be entirely the result of our management of the biology of the mind. Maybe our friends elsewhere have been smart enough – or is it empathic enough? - to avoid the problems arising from maladroit, ignorant or cynical mismanagement of status and have rid themselves of conflictual patterns of behaviour stemming from rigid identity caricatures. Then again, maybe they are up to their tentacles in it.